

Challenges of “Operationalizing” Dynamic System Access Control: Transitioning from ABAC to RAdAC

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ABSTRACT

While the DoD has a strong identity and credential management foundation, much work remains to achieve the DoD access control vision of providing dynamic access control with appropriate granularity. Ongoing access control investments are transitioning from administrators manually provisioning of user accounts to Attribute-Based Access Control (ABAC) capabilities. While this offers significant operational benefits over manual provisioning, ABAC capabilities must evolve. A limiting factor of the ABAC method is its reliance on the availability of authoritative attributes, and the need for access control policies that focus on specific access requests and still result in desired enterprise-wide operations. In today’s DoD mission and business environments, there is a compelling need to provide authorized users, both anticipated and unanticipated, access to sensitive and classified enterprise information and the resources they need, when and where they need it, while preventing disclosure or exploitation by malicious insiders and other adversaries access to the same information. To meet this challenge, a DoD-wide Dynamic Access Management capability is needed by combining ABAC with risk management to achieve Risk Adaptive Access Control (RAdAC).

1.0 INTRODUCTION

To control access to computer systems and networks, and the information and services they provide, system administrators are required to provision accounts to users for systems they access. Much of this is done manually and access attributes are hard-coded per user. Unfortunately the access control mechanisms in place today are no longer sufficient to meet the changing needs of the DoD. As we continue to realize the importance of information to the successful execution of our missions, it is critical that the DoD enhance its access control posture to achieve more dynamic and fine-grained capabilities necessary to protect and ensure the availability of our valuable information assets to the people that need it. [4]

Operational realities and Information Assurance (IA) requirements that must be addressed in providing a Dynamic Access Management capability include:

- Providing dynamic access to enterprise information to people with the appropriate attributes (clearance, citizenship, and organizational membership) while prohibiting access to enterprise information by people and resources that do not meet the access criteria. This fine-grained access control is fundamental to preventing unauthorized disclosure of classified as well as Controlled Unclassified Information (CUI).
- Growing population of users with increased diversity (nationality, organizational affiliation, operational roles, and security clearances).

- Operating at cyber speeds that align with increased mission tempos.
- Maintaining confidence in our information and protecting it from adversary exploitation.
- Accommodating unanticipated users where access rules may have to change in response to geo-political and mission environments.
- Ensuring seamless operations across what have traditionally been sovereign boundaries, while retaining protection of sovereign assets for our allies and the U.S.
- Ensuring the accuracy and integrity of identity information retrieved from “authoritative sources” corresponds to the correct human/non-human entity.

The DoD vision for access control, as one part of the larger Identity and Access Management (IdAM) environment is characterized by:

“...The Department will have the ability to employ fine-grained access policies that provide the necessary control and drive information sharing to the next level.”[1]

2.0 TODAY’S OPERATIONAL ABAC CAPABILITIES

ABAC enforces system access control decisions based on a set of privileges embodied or inferred in characteristics or attributes associated with the requestor, the asset requested, and possibly other pre-established factors as described by access control policies applying to the context of a transaction¹. ABAC promotes the use of attributes for “dynamic decisioning”, which begins to address and answer some of the needs of today’s dynamic environments. In this enterprise-wide environment, it is necessary to coordinate access control in order to meet enterprise governance requirements and support dynamic communities of interest (COI), unanticipated users and unanticipated system/data access.

Currently, there are several initiatives being implemented to demonstrate ABAC solutions. One involves the Department of Homeland Security (DHS), Defense Information Systems Agency (DISA), and the Intelligence Community participating in a Privilege Management pilot. A second initiative involves the National Senior Leadership Decision Support System (NSLDSS) Joint Concept Technology Demonstration (JCTD). This proved that a Service Oriented Enterprise (SOE) based on an ABAC

¹ The fundamental process behind the ABAC method starts with a requester providing his or her identity credentials in an access request to a Policy Enforcement Point (PEP). The PEP queries a Policy Decision Point (PDP) where the attributes and access request are evaluated against the applicable access control policies. After the evaluation, the PDP generates an authorization decision, which is sent to the PEP to enforce.

model using client-side Public Key Infrastructure (PKI) without provisioning users could support the DoD's Enterprise. It drove innovation in attribute availability, policy shortcomings, development techniques, and cooperation across the Enterprise. It is critical that follow-on efforts leverage the reference implementation, as well as, adopt the NSLDSS standards, philosophies, and practices that lead to a more secure DoD Enterprise. [5]

A third initiative involves the Net-Centric Enterprise Services (NCES). The Defense Manpower Data Center (DMDC) Enterprise Identity Attribute Service (EIAS) has been designated as the mechanism to provide the Attribute Service function required for the NCES Service Oriented Architecture Foundation (SOAF) Security capability. The information provided via EIAS can be used to confirm an individual's organizational affiliation needed to support the DoD identity registration process and asset access authorization processes. It provides the capability to cross-reference, share, and distribute identity information, including the DoD Unique Person Identifier, i.e., the DoD Electronic Data Interchange Person Identifier (EDIPI), and the DoD Enterprise Username.

Figure 1 shows the authorization services components with the ABAC model. This highlights the components and flow of data through an ABAC model for an Access Control Point (ACP). The ACP evaluates applicable policy, resource metadata, and subject attributes to determine the access decision whether to allow or deny access. Since identity credentials, attributes and digital policies are relatively static, controls based on ABAC do not easily accommodate dynamic changes that are becoming critical to support existing and projected future mission needs. Note that the ACP can be implemented as a centralized enterprise service or a local implementation.

Figure 1- Authorization Services Components with ABAC
3.0 AN OPERATIONAL PERSPECTIVE ON DYNAMIC ACCESS MANAGEMENT

Making an access decision should be relatively straightforward under normal situations. There is a set of a priori access decision rules that identify factors to be considered. The access mechanism verifies the identity of the entity requesting access, obtaining the decision factors for that entity from authoritative sources, then applies the access rules to formulate an access decision and enforce that decision.

Within some operational environments like the military, drug/law enforcement, intelligence, emergency health care, air traffic

control, there is a distinct possibility for critical operational conditions (maybe even life-and-death situations) where unplanned access decisions may be needed in place of those associated with normal day-to-day routines. Perhaps a soldier's life can be saved by granting him access to highly classified intelligence information even if he does not have a security clearance, or the life of an unconscious patient in a hospital emergency room could be saved by granting a doctor access to the patient's private personal information, even if the doctor is not authorized to access it. Whether the situations are life-threatening or not, some environments will demand more sophisticated approaches than those provided in traditional access schemes, which are not designed to cope with this level of complexity. So why not just grant access whenever there is any doubt about the consequences of denying that access? The answer is that within many of these environments, there may be negative consequences to overriding a traditional access decision that have to be traded off against the perceived benefit of granting that access. For instance, if access is provided to an unauthorized requester, it could jeopardize a mission or create significant vulnerabilities that could perhaps weaken the overarching security posture of the enterprise used by the requester.

3.1 An Operational Challenge Scenario

During a military operation, our tactical intelligence indicates that a location we are holding will be overrun imminently. Our soldiers, or possible allies or coalition partners are very likely to be killed or taken prisoner. These soldiers do not have adequate security clearances to be given access to the intelligence information. Since the systems used by these soldiers do not have the ability to protect this level of sensitive information, providing this access creates vulnerabilities that an adversary could exploit to either gain access to other assets or possibly modify or destroy other information critical to the mission. Divulging the intelligence may save the lives of the deployed soldiers. However, if our adversaries become aware that we have this intelligence, it is likely to tip them off to our intelligence sources and methods. A mission commander (or more likely mission operator) has to make a decision to release or withhold the intelligence information within minutes or less. Does one facet of mission need override the strong possibility of jeopardizing our intelligence collection capabilities, the lives of our intelligence sources, and subsequently the ability to achieve mission success?

3.2 Why We Need RAdAC

Risk Adaptive Access Control (RAdAC) combined with traditional ABAC enables the authorized user to access appropriate level information based on the operational environment in which the user currently located. The fundamental advantage of a RAdAC solution is that it balances operational need with the potential risks that would result if the access were granted. RAdAC can be viewed as an enhancement² to current and planned ABAC IDAM solutions, formulating

² Whether the ABAC solutions can be refined and upgraded or will need to be replaced will actually depend on the nature of the ABAC solution embodiment and the changes needed to shift to a RAdAC process.

access decisions based on the operational threat and mission needs, as well as attribute decision factors. A critical factor for RAdAC is to determine the various factors that measure up the security risk and characterize accurate operational needs of each access decision. Security risk factors identified in this paper are:

- Trust of person/non-person entities (NPE) requesting access
- Sensitivity of information and assets being requested
- Quality of protection that can be afforded to the requested information
- Role of the person/resources
- Criticality of information to the operation
- Uncertainty about environmental conditions, threats, and/or locations
- Heuristics using a history of access decisions (perhaps from audit records) and the impacts to operational missions and enterprise risks.

RAdAC represents a fundamental shift in the way system access control is managed. RAdAC goes beyond the traditional reliance on static identity credentials, attributes and policies. It also considers information about the trustworthiness of machine used by the requester's trustworthiness (e.g., Trusted Platform Module)[2], information about security provisions within the corporate IT infrastructure, and most important, environmental situational inputs that are possible risk factors as input for the decision making process. These situational inputs could include information on the current threat level an organization faces based on data gathered from other sources (e.g., security vendors, Computer Emergency Response Team (CERT), and/or Common Vulnerabilities and Exposures (CVE) from authoritative vulnerability databases). Other inputs could include business or mission criticality of providing requested access (or consequences of denying requested access, mission status, role of requester, assurance level of the requester's identity authentication, and sensitivity of the requested asset and implications if it is gained by an adversary). It uses this information to create an overall quantifiable risk metric associated with granting the access request. It extends upon earlier access control models by introducing these risk assessments, environmental conditions and the concept of "operational need" into the access control decision process. RAdAC also uses situational factors. RAdAC concepts also consider the use of heuristics; considering relevant earlier access decisions that were allowed or denied and the implications or results of those decisions.

After all of this information is gathered, RAdAC combines these factors based on the relevant access control policy to formulate access decisions. The access control policy could include directives for how access control should be handled under a variety of situations and with a variety of risk levels. For example, under normal operating conditions, a person may be able to log into an IT system with a username and password per the normal operating policy, but under heightened threat conditions, RAdAC could enforce a second, stricter policy³ that also requires a digital certificate for two-factor authentication. In

³ Note that it is possible for ABAC to use multiple access control policies for use in various conditions as well, as long as the current condition can be identified external to the ABAC solution.

this example RAdAC policies would be able to specify the set of circumstances under which ordinarily strong access control could be relaxed to allow access based upon a determination of operational need to access a resource, whether it has to calculate it internally or use an authoritative external source. This means that RAdAC allows operational need to override security risk, when necessary, as long as the policies implement the overrides. RAdAC also takes a probabilistic, heuristic approach to determine whether the access should be granted under current operational circumstances. The heuristics include a historical record of access control decisions and machine learning. This means that a RAdAC system will use previous decisions as one input when determining whether access will be granted to a resource in the future.[6]

Figure 2 illustrates a process flow for RAdAC, which shows an event (e.g., terrorist attack, hurricane, DSCA event, etc.) occurring. This occurrence results in a policy change or operational need, which in this example could be initiated by either the Legislative branch or Executive branch of Government. Once it has been determined that a policy needs to be changed, the Digital Policy Management (DPM) enterprise service will convert it from a "human" readable to a "machine" readable form. That allows the policy to be automated and passed via Secure Configuration Management (SCM) to the end point access control mechanism.

Figure 2- RAdAC Model Process Flow

The PvM system is critical for maintaining the security posture for the enterprise supporting the mission, leveraging validated identity credentials, authoritative attributes, metadata, and digital policies. SCM provides asset security compliance status to support an enterprise continuous monitoring capability. Continuous monitoring is the process and technology used to detect compliance and risk issues associated with an organizations operational environment. Audit will establish common processes and procedures to identify security-relevant events, enable audit report access and facilitate the analysis of audit alerts. It also enables historical trends, which may trigger suspicions associated with the newly granted access.

3.3 Why Accept Possible Added Risk

Why add potential risks to the enterprise, the mission and possibly broader national interests that result from allowing someone without proper clearances to access CUI and classified information? A prominent issue facing our Combatant Commands (COCOMs), Military Departments (MILDEPs) and related Agencies is that field commanders need to give access to

and share classified information in less than ideal conditions. A commander may need to allow access to information due to an outbreak, an uprising, or a Humanitarian Assistance and Disaster Relief (HADR) event. People will need access to computers, networks, and/or facilities in a much shorter timeframe than the “traditional” bureaucratic way.

Commanders’ decisions have to be made recognizing the critical operational need to share mission information may outweigh the potential security risks of not providing that access. A basis for making this type of decision has to be based on an understanding of the operational need, the mission impact of granting or denying the access, resultant security risk, policies and operating procedures presiding over the situation and knowledge of the effects of similar decisions made in the past. By allowing access, risks may increase, but when immediate access is needed to accomplish mission needs, the operational needs must outweigh the security risk.

Even though it is essential for a commander to have the ability to make these types of decisions in order to execute their mission needs, it is unlikely they have the comprehensive understanding of all of the security risks that may be impacted with their decision. It is more likely that the commander understands the local implications to changes in access policies, than an in-depth understanding of the ramifications to the overarching enterprise, or possible international impacts that effect operations with allies and coalition partners.

4.0 TRANSITIONING

It is possible that ABAC could achieve the benefits of some aspects of RAdAC to the extent that the operational needs and security risks can be quantified and expressed as attributes, in addition to, the policy rules and language abilities needed to support calculations associated with formulating a more complex access decision. Currently, there are several efforts underway that will quantify factors that are associated with the need and risk. It would be possible and useful to start incorporating operational need and security risk attributes, but work is still needed on capturing, integrating, and preprocessing these as attributes. We also need to develop policy rules that will incorporate their use, and plan for the future development and integration of these factors. Do we need to transition all systems within the DoD to ABAC prior to implementing RAdAC? Can we move directly to RAdAC even if some systems are not supporting ABAC? RAdAC decisions are made based on a number of factors. Figure 3 depicts the RAdAC Functional View. The functional structure allows operational need to enable access and to outweigh security risk in determining access. Operational need was considered in traditional models under the ‘need to know’ guideline, but was used to restrict access rather than to enable it. The operational community is shifting to a “need to share” paradigm, where emphasis is on sharing information whenever possible, and restricting access only when it is warranted.[3] Given its emphasis, operational need must be characterized and parameterized in such a way that the RAdAC process can use it.

RAdAC incorporates a real time, probabilistic determination of security risk into the access control decision rather than just using a hard comparison of the attributes of the subject and object as in traditional models. Using a risk-based approach

RAdAC can be responsive to the broad range of operational situations typical to DoD.

Figure 3: RAdAC Function View

Within the situational factors, the conditions under which the access decision is being made are factored into the process. National, enterprise, or local situations may determine these conditions. Such conditions may dictate whether operational need can outweigh security risk, regardless of the severity of the security risk.

The access control policy specifies the rules for access control for various classes of information objects under different conditions. It allows the enterprise to describe the degree of operational need required to “override” acceptable or normal security risk, and to set acceptable levels of risk. Effectively implementing and managing digital access control policies is a critical element to making the RAdAC model successful.

Within heuristics, knowledge of past access control decisions will be used in making each subsequent decision. Such knowledge can be used to develop better algorithms for determining risk and operational need, and help fine-tune the access control policy to improve the rate of access control decisions that have a positive impact or result.

5.0 CHALLENGES

As with anything new, there are challenges ahead to implement such a process. These challenges could be roadblocks or they could lead to innovative ways to improve our ability to safeguard our nation’s most important data, networks, and facilities.

Is it feasible to make all of the data available that would be needed to make a risk-based decision? More than likely not, but, this is just one of the challenges that needs to be examined when implementing a RAdAC solution. Other challenges facing the execution of RAdAC across the DoD/IC community include the ability to:

- Calculate the security risk of each access decision in real-time
- Determine operational risk
- Quantify trust in someone other than through the process of a security clearance

- Quantify a level of trust from IT components, Trusted Platform Module (TPM), networks, and systems[2]
- Determine the location of the IT components, networks, and systems and being able to quantify the adversarial threat and impact within that location
- Use heuristics when applied to access control decisions and improving those access control decisions
- Revoke access to information to an entity, at anytime, from anywhere.

Implementing RAdAC at this stage may be daunting. Many of the obstacles for a successful implementation are technical in nature. First, integrating the many systems involved in RAdAC will be a challenge, given that they are diverse and data exchange among them has not been standardized. Second, RAdAC relies on digital policies to specify the processing of decision factors in order to determine whether access should be allowed. This will require standardized ways of structuring and exchanging policies, and a means to unequivocally define these digital policies so that the RAdAC system can correctly interpret them. Third, trustworthy sources of user information will need to be made available to the system; the need for trustworthy information about the status, capabilities, and security posture of various parts of the IT infrastructure is equally important. Fourth, since a part of RAdAC's functionality is the ability to adapt to changing environmental conditions, unambiguous mechanisms to describe the various environmental conditions that need to go into an access control decision is also necessary. Again, standardized data exchange formats will determine how robust, adaptable and useful the environment data will be in a RAdAC implementation. Fifth, is the reliance on heuristic in the assessment of whether to allow access to a system. Machine learning, genetic algorithms, and heuristics have come a long way, but, they still have a long way to go before they can be included in RAdAC.

Additionally, there are challenges that are not technical in nature. Challenges related to Policy and laws. Does deploying RAdAC in certain environments violate any laws? Who is held accountable if a security breach were to occur, given the decisions to allow or deny access to a system are automated? Are the system owners, the RAdAC implementers and administrators, and/or the RAdAC system designers ultimately responsible if a breach were to occur? What happens if someone needs immediate access, has the proper clearances and is still denied access to the information needed to perform their mission needs? These questions must be addressed before RAdAC can be widely deployed, and certainly before organizations feel comfortable allowing RAdAC to control access to their sensitive information.

The RAdAC Functional View is depicted in Figure 4, which includes many of the challenges, identified in the call-out boxes. Each phase indicates some type of challenge. These implementation challenges are the beginnings of making RAdAC a reality. Several accomplishments have already been met or are in the making to allow RAdAC to come to fruition.

Figure 4: RAdAC Implementation Challenges

6.0 ACCOMPLISHMENTS/PROGRESS

Although there are numerous challenges and obstacles in the path to fully implement a RAdAC capability, there are several initiatives underway that could accelerate RAdAC's deployment. Many of these initiatives are shown below in Figure 5. Even though there are no commercial standards for implementing RAdAC, there are other standards like Security Content Automation Protocol (SCAP) that are maturing that could help in the delivery of RAdAC. Since continuous monitoring is used to detect compliance and risk issues associated with an organization's operational environment, it can also be used as an input to the risk assessments that are needed in a RAdAC solution.

Other initiatives like the emergence of CUI metadata, Open Accessible Space Information System (OASIS) and eXtensible Access Control Markup Language (XACML) profiles are not in themselves comprehensive RAdAC capabilities, but they do contribute to a RAdAC system solution implementation. Figure 5 overlays these accomplishments and progress being made against the RAdAC Functional View.

Figure 5: Accomplishments Achieved Within Each RADAC Function

7.0 WAY FORWARD & CONCLUDING REMARKS

RAAdAC is a capability that needs to gain recognition within the DoD community, and with this, visibility to encourage the DoD community to establish and execute a phased implementation plan. Some short-term recommendations have been identified. To demonstrate the operational value, assess operational viability and evaluate technical feasibility, we need to implement short-term concept demonstrations, participate in operational exercises and support initial operational deployments that show successes and bring the need for RAAdAC to the forefront.

One way is by determining the operational need to access data. This can be done by influencing the groups working metadata in the DoD to have them consider how to add metadata that aids in determining the criticality of sharing the information and with whom, not just metadata related to restricting who can have it. Perhaps an indication as to what type of data it is, what DoD work roles (e.g., intelligence analyst, plans and operations officer, etc.) might this be valuable to, and maybe some scale similar to the classification scale that indicates the consequence if it's not shared. For example, just as Secret information might indicate that grave harm could occur if the data is compromised, a 'sharing' marking could indicate that serious consequences could occur to the enterprise if the data isn't shared with the right people. The effort would involve defining such metadata and getting policies in place. There is nothing here that is technically challenging from a technology perspective.

A second way to implement a short-term success is by determining the trustworthiness of a person's identity other than through a security clearance. The foundation of the security posture of an enterprise is a trustworthy process for identifying each human and Non-Person Entity (NPE). We have to make sure that proliferation of identity theft, which has become a national problem, cannot be translated into threats to the integrity of the entity identification process adopted for the enterprise. It is amazing how much information can be found about someone from various sources on the Internet. For instance, if someone were to request his or her annual credit report online, one would

need to provide some personal information. Some of that information would include full name, address, social security number, date of birth, and possibly a place of birth. The application will then proceed to verify your identity by asking a series of "challenge" questions. One set of questions may provide you with a list of addresses and ask you to identify which one had been your residence at some time in the past (i.e. what was your address prior to your current residence?). Another question may have a similar list and ask to identify which one had never been one of your residences. There are others too like, "Have you ever taken a loan or mortgage out with any one of the following companies", and the answer to that may be none of the above. It is a method to try to "trick" you into picking something on the list. It just indicates how much information is available. A lot of information can be found on an individual within a short amount of time. So, some work could be done to figure out how to establish some level of trust in a person (or not) through available information online. It is almost like doing an instant clearance. Again, this is not technically impossible and could provide important information in a short amount of time.

One more area that needs to be worked pertains to the quantification and determination of acceptable risk levels. What does that mean with respect to security? How can thresholds be defined in policies if we do not have any idea if a risk level of 0.8 is acceptable? Or is 0.9 more acceptable? What does that even mean? The safety world provides some indications of how such numbers can be valuable and what levels are acceptable from a reliability or safety perspective. This has not been done in the security world to any extent and should be a major area to focus if RAAdAC were to be implemented across the DoD.

RAAdAC represents a fundamental shift in the way access control is managed. RAAdAC goes beyond the traditional reliance on static identity credentials, attributes and policies. It also considers information about the trustworthiness of machine used by the requester's trustworthiness, information about security provisions within the corporate IT infrastructure and most important, environmental situational inputs that are possible risk factors as input for the decision making process. RAAdAC is a capability that will need attention in the near future. As access control requirements need more real-time intervention, RAAdAC will come to the forefront of access control capabilities. Operational needs will need to be considered for the potential to outweigh the security risks involved with allowing access. RAAdAC can be beneficial to communities beyond those within the DoD (e.g., banking and financial industries, and companies holding intellectual properties). Even though RAAdAC is not a deployable capability at the present time, many accomplishments have been achieved and much progress has been made in foundational capabilities that will make it possible to implement RAAdAC as the next major access control mechanism. The DoD, IC and other U.S. Government communities cannot afford another incident like WikiLeaks. By implementing access control mechanisms like RAAdAC, each access decision request will have to be judged based on, "Does the operational need truly outweigh the security risks?"

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